

THE ADMINISTRATION OF LAND TAXES AND THE CONCEPT OF REVIVED LANDS IN *KITAB AL-KHARAJ*

Dimas Indra Pratama

Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, Indonesia

Corresponding author: dimasgaspoll35@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper explores the administration of land tax and the concept of revived lands as detailed in *Kitab al-Kharaj*, a key work on early Islamic economic jurisprudence authored by Abū-Yūsuf. The study focuses on how the principles outlined in *Kitab al-Kharaj* addressed the management and taxation of land within the early Islamic state. It examines the criteria for determining land ownership and the conditions under which barren or uncultivated lands could be claimed and revived by individuals. Additionally, the paper analyzes the implementation of land tax (Kharāj) and its impact on agricultural productivity and resource distribution. By reviewing the administrative practices and theoretical underpinnings presented in *Kitab al-Kharaj*, the paper aims to provide insights into the early Islamic approach to land management and taxation, and how these practices influenced the economic policies of the time. This analysis contributes to a deeper understanding of historical land administration and its implications for contemporary discussions on land taxation and resource management.

Keywords: *Revived Lands, Administration of Land Taxes, Kitab Al-Kharaj*

I. INTRODUCTION

The administration of land taxes and the concept of revived lands (ihya al-mawat) in Islamic jurisprudence, as exemplified in Abu Yusuf's *Kitab al-Kharaj*, played a crucial role in shaping economic and social structures in Islamic societies during the Abbasid Caliphate. The kharaj tax system, which included taxes like ushr and jizya, was a significant revenue source for the Islamic state, particularly in agricultural regions. This tax was levied based on land productivity and ownership, highlighting the importance of understanding local agricultural conditions and land usage patterns for effective tax administration (Hakim, 2024). The complexity of the land tax system required a well-structured bureaucracy to manage the collection of taxes from both Muslim and non-Muslim landowners. The revenue generated from these taxes contributed to the economic policies of the Abbasid state and provided insights into broader principles of Islamic governance and law (Hakim, 2024). The

utilization of abandoned lands for productive projects, as discussed in the context of Shariah principles, aligns with the concept of revived lands (*ihya al-mawat*) in Islamic jurisprudence. This approach not only adheres to Shariah principles but also contributes to poverty alleviation efforts, showcasing the multifaceted applications of Islamic legal principles in addressing societal challenges (Baharuddin, 2023). Furthermore, the incorporation of local wisdom elements in Islamic jurisprudence is highlighted as a means to enrich Islamic law, making it more relevant to contemporary society and ensuring its continued influence and effectiveness. This emphasis on integrating local knowledge underscores the adaptive nature of Islamic jurisprudence to address evolving societal needs and contexts (Marinsah, 2024). The historical significance of land taxation and the concept of revived lands in Islamic jurisprudence, as outlined in *Kitab al-Kharaj*, underscores the intricate relationship between economic policies, governance principles, and legal frameworks in Islamic societies during the Abbasid Caliphate. These concepts not only reflect the economic realities of the time but also offer enduring insights into the principles that guided Islamic governance and law.

The concept of revived lands (*ihya al-mawat*) as addressed in *Kitab al-Kharaj* by Abu Yusuf highlights the practice of reclaiming and cultivating uncultivated lands, incentivizing individuals to gain ownership through their efforts. This concept not only facilitated the expansion of agricultural frontiers during the early Islamic period but also reflected Islamic principles promoting the productive use of land (Hakim, 2024). The administration of land taxes, including the *kharaj* tax system, was integral to the economic foundations of the Islamic state, balancing state revenue needs with the rights and responsibilities of landowners. Understanding these principles is essential for comprehending the economic structures of early Islamic societies and the enduring influence of Islamic legal thought on land use and taxation (Hakim, 2024). Moreover, the utilization of abandoned lands in accordance with Shariah principles, as discussed in the context of *ihya al-mawat*, aligns with the broader principles of Islamic governance and economic prosperity (Baharuddin, 2023). By incorporating local wisdom elements into Islamic jurisprudence, scholars have enriched Islamic law, making it more relevant to contemporary society and ensuring its continued effectiveness in addressing societal challenges (Marinsah, 2024). The study of revived lands and the administration of land taxes as outlined in *Kitab al-Kharaj* provides valuable insights into the economic history and legal theory of early Islamic states. These concepts not only shed light on the economic policies of the Abbasid Caliphate but also offer enduring principles that continue to shape discussions on land use and taxation in modern Islamic societies.

This investigative study aims to explore the administration of land taxes and the concept of revived lands as outlined in *Kitab al-Kharaj*. By examining the historical context, legal principles, and practical applications of these concepts, the study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of how land taxation and land use policies were implemented in early Islamic societies. The study will analyze the relationship

between the state and landowners, the impact of land taxes on agricultural productivity, and the role of *ihya al-mawat* in expanding agricultural territories.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The administration of land taxes and the concept of revived lands (*ihya al-mawat*) as discussed in *Kitab al-Kharaj* have been subjects of extensive scholarly investigation, as they are integral to understanding the fiscal policies and economic strategies of early Islamic states. This literature review explores key themes within the existing body of scholarship, highlights the contributions of various scholars to the understanding of these concepts, and identifies gaps in the research that this study seeks to address.

2.1. Land Taxation in Early Islamic Governance

Land taxation, particularly the kharaj tax, has been a significant focus in the study of early Islamic governance, particularly during the Abbasid Caliphate. Scholars have delved into the role of the kharaj tax as a primary revenue system that financed the Islamic state, supporting its bureaucratic and military infrastructure (Schibille et al., 2018). The implementation of kharaj varied across regions due to diverse agricultural practices, economic conditions, and social structures, with scholars analyzing how kharaj and ushr were balanced to ensure state revenue without overburdening the agricultural sector (Schibille et al., 2018). Furthermore, the literature emphasizes the importance of fairness and social justice in land taxation, with Islamic jurists advocating for just tax collection based on land productivity and ethical standards (Schibille et al., 2018).

The relationship between land taxation and social justice in Islamic governance has been a recurring theme in scholarly discussions, reflecting broader Islamic principles of fairness and equity in economic transactions (Schibille et al., 2018). The emphasis on fairness in tax collection, as highlighted in works like *Kitab al-Kharaj*, underscores the significance of ethical tax practices in early Islamic governance (Schibille et al., 2018). This concern for justice in tax collection aligns with Islamic principles and the need to ensure that taxes were levied based on the land's productive capacity, reflecting a balance between state revenue generation and the welfare of the agricultural sector (Schibille et al., 2018).

2.2. The Concept of Revived Lands (*Ihya al-Mawat*)

The concept of *ihya al-mawat*, focusing on the revival of unused lands through cultivation or development, has been a subject of scholarly inquiry within Islamic governance. This principle, deeply rooted in Islamic law, not only served as a legal framework but also as a practical policy to stimulate agricultural expansion and economic progress (Kim, 2022). Scholars have examined how *ihya al-mawat* facilitated land ownership acquisition for individuals, aligning with legal and economic considerations (Suhendra, 2017). The implementation of *ihya al-mawat* varied across Islamic regions and periods, influenced by local conditions, state

policies, and land availability, leading to diverse interpretations of its impact on agricultural economies (Rusli, 2008).

The significance of *ihya al-mawat* in promoting agricultural growth and addressing land ownership issues has been underscored in the literature (Syarbaini, 2024). This concept has been crucial in regions where agricultural expansion was essential for sustaining populations and ensuring food security (Mohamad & Muslim, 2020). Additionally, the application of *ihya al-mawat* has been explored in the context of government power and land management, reflecting its practical implications within Islamic governance (Serji et al., 2020).

2.3. The Integration of Fiscal and Legal Frameworks

The integration of fiscal and legal frameworks within Islamic governance, as exemplified by *Kitab al-Kharaj*, has been a significant area of scholarly investigation. This treatise is renowned for harmonizing fiscal policies with Islamic legal principles, demonstrating how economic strategies were intricately intertwined with religious and ethical considerations (Tofan et al., 2020). Scholars have delved into how *Kitab al-Kharaj* navigates the balance between state revenue requirements and the rights of landowners, emphasizing the importance of just and equitable taxation in alignment with broader Islamic governance objectives (Moore & Newsome, 2018). This integration of fiscal and legal frameworks has been identified as a distinguishing feature of Islamic economic thought, setting it apart from contemporary systems (Wildowicz-Giegiel, 2019).

Moreover, the legal discussions within *Kitab al-Kharaj* regarding land ownership, taxation, and the rights of landowners have garnered significant scholarly attention. The treatise offers detailed guidance on various aspects of land ownership, tax imposition conditions, and the legal obligations of both the state and landholders, showcasing a comprehensive legal framework deeply rooted in Islamic jurisprudence (Onofrei et al., 2021). This legal framework has not only been studied in its historical context but also for its enduring influence on subsequent Islamic legal thought, highlighting its lasting impact on legal and fiscal practices within Islamic societies (Beuermann et al., 2021).

2.4. Impact on Social and Economic Development

The social and economic implications of land taxation and the concept of revived lands have been subjects of scholarly exploration, shedding light on their impacts on wealth distribution, resource allocation, and socio-economic dynamics within Islamic societies. The administration of land taxes, such as *kharaj*, played a pivotal role in shaping the distribution of resources and wealth, with studies indicating that the tax system could either exacerbate or alleviate social inequalities based on its implementation and perceived fairness (Schwerhoff et al., 2019).

Similarly, the concept of *ihya al-mawat* had significant social ramifications by offering individuals opportunities to acquire land and enhance their socio-economic status. However, the success of this policy was contingent on various factors like

resource availability, state support, and individual investment capacity, underscoring the complex interplay between land ownership, taxation, and social dynamics (Lu et al., 2023). Scholars have scrutinized how these policies influenced different segments of society, highlighting the intricate relationship between land ownership, taxation, and socio-economic development (Kristiyanto, 2021).

The broader implications of land taxation and revived lands have been examined through various lenses, including their impacts on economic growth, resource management, and social equity. Studies have delved into the effects of land use changes on economic development, the role of land financialization in urban growth, and the mechanisms through which transportation land transfers influence economic growth (Hubar et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2021). Furthermore, research has explored the relationship between urban land taxation and economic development, emphasizing the importance of understanding the impacts of tax reforms on urban economic dynamics (Agustina, 2024).

2.5. Gaps and Future Directions

To address the gaps in the existing literature on land taxation and revived lands in Islamic jurisprudence, it is essential to delve into the regional variations in the implementation of *kharaj* and *ihya al-mawat*. While the principles from *Kitab al-Kharaj* are well-established, their application has shown significant diversity across various Islamic regions and historical periods. This variation underscores the importance of conducting further research to comprehend how local conditions influenced the administration of land taxes and land reclamation policies in different contexts. Moreover, comparative studies between Islamic land taxation systems and those of contemporary societies could offer valuable insights into the distinctiveness of the Islamic approach to land taxation and property rights. By exploring these comparative perspectives, researchers can shed light on how Islamic economic principles have influenced broader legal and economic systems, contributing to a more nuanced understanding of the economic foundations of Islamic governance. Furthermore, interdisciplinary research integrating historical, legal, economic, and social viewpoints is crucial for gaining a holistic understanding of the impact of land taxes and revived lands on Islamic societies (Borhan & Aziz, 2012). Such an approach would not only enrich the scholarship on Islamic governance and economic history but also provide a comprehensive analysis of how these fiscal and legal frameworks shaped early Islamic societies and continue to influence contemporary Islamic legal and economic systems.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative research design to examine the concepts of revived lands and the administration of land tax as presented in *Kitab Al-Kharaj*, focusing on their implementation and relevance in the context of Islamic governance. The research will involve an in-depth content analysis of *Kitab Al-Kharaj*, with a particular

emphasis on primary source material to uncover the underlying principles guiding land revival and taxation.

Thematic analysis will be utilized to categorize and interpret key themes related to land ownership, revival of unused lands (*ihya' al-mawat*), and the administration of land tax (*kharaj*). A comprehensive literature review of both classical and contemporary scholarly interpretations will supplement the primary analysis, providing a broader context for understanding Abu Yusuf's approach to land management. Ethical considerations, including respect for intellectual property and the faithful representation of Islamic legal principles, will be strictly observed throughout the study. This methodological approach will offer valuable insights into the historical and legal foundations of land revival and taxation in Islamic law, with implications for modern land administration practices in Muslim-majority societies.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Taxation and Ownership of Barren Lands: Abù-Yùsuf's Perspective on Economic Efficiency and Land Revival in Islamic Law

Abù-Yùsuf, a prominent Islamic jurist, addressed the relationship between tax policy and economic efficiency, particularly concerning uncultivated and unused lands. He began by defining barren lands as those that show no signs of construction or cultivation, or that are used for public utilities such as parks, graveyards, forests, or pastures. Importantly, these lands were not in anyone's possession. Abù-Yùsuf then explored the question of what the most suitable tax policy should be for such lands, especially when they are revived and put to productive use.

According to Abù-Yùsuf, the general rule was that anyone who revives barren land becomes its legitimate owner. This view is rooted in the idea that by bringing the land into productive use, the individual earns the right to claim ownership. However, there were some conditions attached to this principle. The caliph, as the ruler, held the authority to grant the land to others, lease it, or make any decisions that would benefit the public. If someone intended to revive barren land and claim ownership, Abù-Yùsuf suggested that permission from the caliph was necessary, particularly to prevent conflicts of interest or competition over the land. This requirement for permission contrasts with the Sunnah, the traditional practices of the Prophet Muhammad, which generally did not mandate such approval. However, Abù-Yùsuf argued that if there were no disputes or harm to others, the Prophet's general practice should apply, and permission would not be needed.

Once the land was revived and cultivated, the type of tax imposed depended on the category of the land. If the land fell under the category of "ushr" land, a one-tenth tax (*ushr*) was to be imposed. If the land was classified as "Kharàj" land, the *Kharàj* tax, which was typically higher, would be levied. The distinction between these two types of land was significant in Islamic tax law, with *ushr* land generally being land owned by Muslims and *Kharàj* land being land under the control of non-Muslims.

In cases where the revived land was part of the conquered territories, different rules applied. If the caliph decided to distribute the conquered land to the Muslim conquerors, after deducting the state's one-fifth share (Khums), the reviver would pay the ushr tax or a reduced rate depending on the irrigation conditions. However, if the caliph chose to leave the conquered land in the hands of its non-Muslim owners, the reviver would be subject to the Kharàj tax.

Abù-Yùsuf's views on land revival and taxation highlight the balance between encouraging the productive use of land and ensuring that tax policies are fair and efficient. His approach also reflects a concern for preventing disputes and ensuring that the public interest is protected in the process of land revival. This framework provided a foundation for land ownership and taxation in Islamic law, influencing how barren lands were managed and taxed in the early Islamic state.

4.2. Abù-Yùsuf's Reforms on Kharàj Administration: Ensuring Fairness and Preventing Injustice in Land Taxation

Abù-Yùsuf, a prominent Islamic scholar, provided detailed insights into the administration of the Kharàj, a land tax levied on non-Muslim-owned lands or lands conquered and left in the hands of the original owners. His views focused on ensuring that the tax system was fair, transparent, and free from corruption. One of his key principles was that no Kharàj administrator or governor had the authority to exempt anyone from paying the Kharàj tax without explicit permission from the Caliph. This measure was intended to prevent any abuse of power or favoritism, ensuring that the tax system remained consistent and just across the board. Likewise, Abù-Yùsuf emphasized that no individual should accept a tax exemption if they knew it was granted without the proper authorization from the Caliph. Exemptions could only be justified if they served the greater benefit of the community.

Abù-Yùsuf also addressed the issue of converting land from Kharàj to ushr land (land owned by Muslims that was subject to a lower tax rate) or vice versa. He believed that such conversions were generally impermissible unless specific conditions were met. For example, if a person who owned ushr land purchased neighboring Kharàj land and combined the two, the land would be treated as ushr land, and the lower tax rate would apply. Conversely, if someone who owned Kharàj land acquired ushr land and merged it with their existing property, the combined land would be taxed at the higher Kharàj rate. This policy ensured that land classification and tax obligations were clear and consistent.

A significant concern for Abù-Yùsuf was the practice of using intermediaries in the collection of land taxes. During the Umayyad and Abbasid caliphates, it was common for intermediaries to act as agents between the Treasury and taxpayers. These intermediaries would pay the taxes to the government on behalf of the landowners, often in advance, and then collect the taxes from the actual taxpayers. While this system was convenient for the Treasury, as it ensured timely tax payments, it had severe drawbacks. The intermediaries frequently charged landowners more than the actual tax due, leading to exploitation and injustice. Abù-Yùsuf strongly

opposed this system, arguing that it led to the "devastation of the country and the destruction of the subjects." He believed that the use of intermediaries distorted the tax system and caused undue hardship for taxpayers. As a result, Abù-Yùsuf advocated for the abolition of this practice, recommending that taxes be paid directly by the taxpayers to the Treasury without the involvement of intermediaries.

In summary, Abù-Yùsuf's reforms on Kharàj administration aimed to create a more equitable and just tax system. By ensuring that tax exemptions were properly authorized, land classifications were clearly defined, and intermediaries were removed from the tax collection process, he sought to protect the rights of taxpayers and maintain the integrity of the land tax system. His recommendations were driven by a commitment to fairness and the well-being of the community, principles that continue to influence Islamic legal and financial practices today.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, Abù-Yùsuf's perspectives on the administration of Kharàj taxation reflect a strong commitment to fairness, transparency, and justice in the land tax system. He advocated for strict adherence to authorized procedures, preventing unauthorized tax exemptions, and ensuring that land classifications were respected. His opposition to the use of intermediaries in tax collection, due to their potential for exploitation, highlights his concern for the well-being of taxpayers and the economic stability of the state. To further these principles in contemporary contexts, it is recommended that modern tax systems prioritize direct transactions between taxpayers and authorities, eliminate unnecessary intermediaries, and ensure that any tax exemptions or adjustments are clearly justified and authorized to prevent abuse and maintain public trust in the fiscal system.

REFERENCES

- Agustina, L. (2024). Analysis of self-regulation in the rencong telang islamic society perspective of social cognitive theory. *Empathy Jurnal Fakultas Psikologi*, 6(2), 184. <https://doi.org/10.12928/empathy.v6i2.27256>
- Baharuddin, A. (2023). Interdisciplinary insights into syariah and legal discourse: navigating critical dimensions, contemporary challenges, and global impact. *Malaysian Journal of Syariah and Law*, 11(2), v-x. <https://doi.org/10.33102/mjssl.vol11no2.706>
- Beuermann, D., Schwartz, M., Reyes-Tagle, G., Silvani, C., Ospina, L., Fajgenbaum, J., ... & Beck, T. (2021). Economic institutions for a resilient caribbean. <https://doi.org/10.18235/0003053>
- Borhan, J. and Aziz, M. (2012). Agriculture and its contribution from the islamic economics perspective. *Jurnal Teknologi*. <https://doi.org/10.11113/jt.v50.184>
- Hakim, R. (2024). Imām al-māwardī's view on the concept of taxation (kharaj) in al-aḥkām sulṭhāniyyah. *Journal of Islamic Thought and Civilization*, 14(1), 266-282. <https://doi.org/10.32350/jitc.141.16>

- Hubar, Y., Hulko, O., Khavar, Y., Vynarchyk, L., & Sai, V. (2019). Geodesy and cartography.. <https://doi.org/10.24425/gac.2020.131086>
- Kim, S. (2022). A study on the regulations and application of islamiclaw on mawat land between the 7th and early 8th centuries. *The Institute of Middle Eastern Affairs*, 21(3), 177-206. <https://doi.org/10.52891/jmea.2022.21.3.177>
- Kristiyanto, K. (2021). Wastewater management to conservation and it's coping to climate change impacts.. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202103.0102.v1>
- Lu, J., Wang, K., & Liu, H. (2023). Land development rights, spatial injustice, and the economic development in net-incremental reduction regions of construction land: evidence from shanghai, china. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(3), 2560. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20032560>
- Marinsah, S. (2024). Consideration of local wisdom elements in the concept of fiqh sabahi: a literature review. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 14(3). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v14-i3/20773>
- Mohamad, Z. and Muslim, N. (2020). Exploration of land and power of government: syarak perspective. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 10(11). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v10-i11/8158>
- Moore, S. and Newsome, K. (2018). Paying for free delivery: dependent self-employment as a measure of precarity in parcel delivery. *Work Employment and Society*, 32(3), 475-492. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950017018755664>
- Onofrei, M., Toader, T., Vatamanu, A., & Oprea, F. (2021). Impact of governments' fiscal behaviors on public finance sustainability: a comparative study. *Sustainability*, 13(7), 3739. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13073739>
- Rusli, R. (2008). Fikih ekologi dan kearifan tradisional: tinjauan terhadap konsep ihyā al-mawāt dan hiimâ. *Hunafa Jurnal Studia Islamika*, 5(3), 287. <https://doi.org/10.24239/jsi.v5i3.176.287-298>
- Schibille, N., Meek, A., Wypyski, M., Kröger, J., Rosser-Owen, M., & Haddon, R. (2018). The glass walls of samarra (iraq): ninth-century abbasid glass production and imports. *Plos One*, 13(8), e0201749. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0201749>
- Schwerhoff, G., Edenhofer, O., & Fleurbaey, M. (2019). Taxation of economic rents. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 34(2), 398-423. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joes.12340>
- Serji, R., Mohamad, M., & Hussein, S. (2020). Pemakaian sistem torrens dalam perundangan tanah malaysia dan kesannya terhadap ihyā' al-mawāt. *Al-Irsyad Journal of Islamic and Contemporary Issues*, 5(2), 463-471. <https://doi.org/10.53840/alirsyad.v5i2.152>
- Suhendra, A. (2017). Models of land ownership in islam: analysis on hadis ihyā' al-mawāt. *Esensia Jurnal Ilmu-Ilmu Ushuluddin*, 18(2), 189-199. <https://doi.org/10.14421/esensia.v18i2.1480>

- Syarbaini, A. (2024). Ihya' al-mawat menurut hukum ekonomi syariah (dalam fiqh islam) ditinjau dari undang-undang pokok agraria dan undang-undang kehutanan. *HEI EMA*, 3(2), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.61393/heiema.v3i2.240>
- Tofan, M., Onofrei, M., & Vatamanu, A. (2020). Fiscal responsibility legal framework—new paradigm for fiscal discipline in the eu. *Risks*, 8(3), 79. <https://doi.org/10.3390/risks8030079>
- Wei, L., Zhang, Z., & Zhou, Y. (2021). Policy strategies to revive rural land in peri-metropolitan towns: resource identification, capitalization, and financialization. *Land*, 10(2), 132. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land10020132>
- Wildowicz-Giegiel, A. (2019). The role of independent fiscal councils in improving fiscal performance of the european union countries. *Equilibrium*, 14(4), 611-630. <https://doi.org/10.24136/eq.2019.029>
- Wu, X., Wang, Y., & Hong-bo, Z. (2022). Does economic growth lead to an increase in cultivated land pressure? evidence from china. *Land*, 11(9), 1515. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11091515>